

IMPROVING THE PUBLIC EDUCATION SYSTEM BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT APPROACHES

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Abstract: *This article will talk about the importance of educational system management and its types. Particular attention is paid to the management of a school with secondary educational institutions in the system of continuing education. It has been discussed that the management of general secondary schools is an urgent issue of the day, in order to perfect their characteristics and possible areas of development. Aspects of importance in school management have been highlighted and touched on the development of management strategies, ranging from those responsible for school management and their individual characteristics.*

Keywords: *modernization, school activities, innovative approach, cluster, innovative cluster of pedagogical education, factors, "school-laboratory", mechanisms of innovative experience, democratization, competition, analysis.*

In the theory of educational management, its uniqueness is manifested in different approaches to management classified according to certain criteria. These approaches determine the essence of the management process and can serve as a subject of analysis in the process of historical-pedagogical research of its evolution, perform the function of qualifying the leading paradigm of this management. Undoubtedly, each of them brought a certain benefit at one or another historical stage in the process of formation of management.

Many reforms in the education system of our republic serve to eliminate the shortcomings in the provision of communication and coherence between the types of education in the field of personnel training. Today, as a result of not fully taking into account the socio-economic uniqueness and demand and needs of the regions in the state policy on personnel training, as a result of the lack of in-depth study of the demand and supply in the labor market, there were deficiencies related to the imbalance in the distribution of personnel across the regions. This is the reason why the need for teaching staff in some regions has not been met for years.

It is known from the experience of countries with high intellectual potential that if the unity and connection between science, education and production is established, it will be possible to train qualified personnel in this direction, ensure their employment, and implement structural changes in the country's economy. The creation of new mechanisms, especially in the development of the continuous education system, has become a vital necessity of today's globalization processes, and this, in turn, requires the improvement of the quality of education and its modernization. The influence of the lifestyle of general secondary educational institutions on the effectiveness of the educational process is of particular importance in pedagogy.

Leaders of educational institutions should develop the lifestyle of the school in connection with the quality of the educational environment, cooperation and collaboration. The content and organization of school life, technological training and management, the content of the teacher training system are among the conditions for the development of school activities..

Most of the research conducted on the effective organization and development of school activities used the following research methods:

- conceptual and terminological analysis of comparative historical, philosophical, pedagogical, social, cultural, literature;

- analysis of modern educational practices;
- modeling (used as a method of studying the system ,and the resulting school structure model served the purpose of comparing school structures from different periods);
- empirical (analysis and synthesis of the experience of school life, study of materials and the results of educational activities of schools, analysis of documents, normative-methodological foundations of the school, regular observations).

In modern science and practice, various scientific spaces are created, a circle of ideas about the need for a targeted formation of an effective organization of school activities is created, and conditions are created for updating the structures of certain educational institutions. At the same time, the study of scientific literature, research, school practice, to varying degrees of regulatory documents, the determination of the prospects for the development of education, the development of national school life in a modern way indicate the presence of a number of contradictions. Including:

- the absence of a collaborative unified scientific theory of the development of the activities of schools as a social and pedagogical phenomenon. (Assumes the formation of such a structure that ensures the spiritual and moral progress and upbringing of the individual between the requirements of society and the state);

- the theory of effective formation and development of the activities of schools and the objective needs of internal education in the study of historical and pedagogical practice and the lack of research data;

- in the history of national pedagogy, the successful experience in the formation of the effective activity of schools and the lack of attention to the creation of high performance school models in modern pedagogical practice;

- in such a change of school structures, the theoretical underdevelopment of trends in the development of modern social programs and school structures

corresponding to the multifaceted life of society, etc.

Overcoming these contradictions requires an increase in the volume of scientific and theoretical and practical research in this direction and their study.

In the practice of modern schools, the study of the trend of school development and changes in school life can occur under the influence of innovations in the content created as a result of the efforts of certain teachers. The leading trend in the development of school structures is the trends of integrative importance arising from the priorities of the educational policy. The effective development of the educational sphere on the basis of integrative principles requires the development of state educational standards, the identification of priority areas of educational activities in educational institutions, the improvement of cooperation between higher educational institutions, the creation of “school-laboratory” complexes within the educational network, the establishment of educational services, resource centers.

Integration processes in an educational institution are ensured by the adoption of school standards for the content and organization of the educational process. Determination of the value advantage of an educational institution, such as the definition of the content of the joint activities of schoolchildren, the creation of a basis for the unification of the school organization, the development of general approaches to the formation of the school structure. In the school, integration processes are carried out through unequal education, through intergenerational communication. The process of differentiation in the field of education is associated with the typicality and diversity of educational institutions, the introduction of different forms of ownership, and different priorities. Differentiation at the level of the educational institution is related to the different educational needs of students, expressed in the need to create flexible schools, youth schools, with different individual and age-related psycho-physiological characteristics.

In addition, we must highlight the interrelated multi-structural nature of the integration processes that carry out the leading trend in the development of school life. we must keep in mind.

A democratic way of school life is a condition for the formation of Public Policy and civil society, in which a graduate enters more life, introducing democracy and spiritual and moral culture, first of all, his thoughts in the family, in the economic and political spheres of life. Democratization of school life implies the involvement of the school in social life. This task is solved by democratization of school management, expansion of Free management of the educational institution, the conditions of cooperation of all members in the field of education, the conditions for the organization of an indicative basis for joint actions, as well as the creation of incentive conditions for the joint implementation of such conditions as self-government, self-assessment.

One of the scopes of research conducted in "school-laboratories" formed as one of the main factors of the implementation of the activity of the innovation cluster of pedagogical education is to determine the factors affecting the provision of quality education and take measures to solve them. Part of this research is the continuous education system in Bukhara region. aimed at improving quality and efficiency.

One of the social factors in the development of school activities is competitive action. The development potential of the multi-oriented education system is characteristic of competitive action, as a result of which educational and social needs are determined in the school.

Thus, the introduction of leading trends in the development of school activities is carried out through the system of state institutions and organizations of individual teachers (heads of educational institutions, students, parents) both under the influence of innovations in the structure of the school's lifestyle.

Thus, the program for the development of an educational institution in

modern conditions is an innovative mechanism that helps an educational institution to modernize its educational activities in accordance with state, regional and city requirements for the results of educational activities. In our opinion, it is very important to once again pay attention to the separation of the content of two documents in an educational institution: the educational program and the development programs. The content of the educational activity is regulated by the educational program - a document that defines the goals, content, technologies, and results of changes of the student and the student in the course of the educational activity. The content of this document includes licensing and state accreditation of the educational institution in accordance with the state educational standard, the structure of the basic general education program.

In conclusion, the development program describes the changes in the infrastructure of the educational institution that ensures the implementation of the educational program. The relevance of educational goals, innovativeness of content, modernity of educational technologies and teaching-methodical complexes used, i.e., all aspects that justify the relevance and modernity of education can be revealed. In the development program, it is necessary to focus on changing the legal, organizational, financial, management and material conditions of providing the educational process in the direction of increasing the quality, convenience and efficiency.

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